

Review

Alleviating Urban Heat Island Effect: based on the “Green Roof” Project Policy

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Abstract: The urban heat island effect is one of the biggest climate problems faced by cities around the world in their development process. Establishing a 'green roof' can lower local temperatures, save energy costs, and reduce urban stormwater runoff, which has many benefits for mitigating the urban heat island effect. The author found through analyzing the incentive or mandatory measures taken by four typical cities in the United States to carry out green roof projects that: on the one hand, various measures have played a strong role in promoting the development of green roof projects; On the other hand, in the process of policy implementation, there have also been issues such as insufficient assessment of local ecology and a one-sided emphasis on “distributive justice” while neglecting “environmental justice”.

Keywords: Green roofs: urban heat island effect: environmental justice; Municipal construction

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Accepted: 01 December, 2024; **Published:** 08 Decemmber, 2024

How to cite this article: Md Joynal Abedin Roky, Md Taruk Aziz, Md Sajibur Rahman Sajib (2024). Alleviating Urban Heat Island Effect: based on the “Green Roof” Project Policy. *North American Academic Research*, 7(12), 11-16. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14293762>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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1. Introduction

The urban heat island effect refers to the phenomenon where the temperature in the city center is significantly higher than that in the suburbs due to a large amount of artificial heating, or due to the increase of high heat storage materials such as roads and buildings and the reduction of green spaces in urban areas. Due to the continuous expansion of modern cities and the high concentration of population, the natural environment beneath the city, such as green spaces, forests, lakes, etc., has undergone fundamental changes. Dry, dense, hard, and heavy building materials such as asphalt, bricks, metal sheets, cement, etc. are gradually replacing the original moist and loose vegetation and soil. One of the main causes of urban heat island effect is the widespread use of non-reflective materials that absorb and retain heat on natural surfaces. In addition, when the natural surface is covered by these materials, rainwater will be difficult to retain in the soil, and the amount of water available for evaporation or transpiration will further decrease, resulting in a reduced cooling effect. Therefore, the solar energy originally consumed during the evaporation process is instead retained as additional heat.

2. Overview of “Green Roofs” Projects in Countries Around the World

In response to this change, urban green infrastructure (UGI) is considered a vital component of urban and public service policies by decision-makers around the world. In the past few decades, Europe, North America, East Asia, and other regions have been committed to developing and promoting new UGI projects through financial support and policy incentives, such as green roofs, green walls, urban community gardens, etc. Among them, green roofs are the most common, which can effectively reduce the air and surface temperature in the area, protect biodiversity, and alleviate the impact of climate change and urban heat island effect. Green roof is a rooftop ecosystem covered by vegetation that is functionally integrated with the roof area. Green roofs can maintain the sustainable development of cities by reducing rainwater runoff and lowering temperatures. In addition, multiple studies have shown that green roofs provide many benefits for people under the roof in terms of quality of life, residents' mental health and happiness, emotional relief, and rest.

Based on this, many developed countries have long formulated various policies to support the development of "green roof" projects. For example, the German government has been providing support and subsidies for the green roof industry since the 1970s. Tokyo, Japan introduced a regulation in 2001 that new buildings over 1000 square meters should have at least 20% green roofs. In 2009, the city of Toronto, Canada began mandating that residential and industrial buildings must have a certain area of green roofs; In 2015, France proposed a new legislative proposal requiring all new buildings constructed thereafter to adopt green roofs or solar roofs. As the world's largest economic power, the United States announced its withdrawal from the Paris Climate Agreement in June 2017. Many cities, such as Philadelphia, New York, Chicago, Atlanta, etc., have separately committed to achieving the greenhouse gas emission targets required by the agreement and promised to build more green buildings to alleviate the urban heat island effect. This has also become one of the hottest topics in current municipal discussions. This article analyzes and introduces the relevant policies of typical cities such as Seattle, Denver, New York, and Chicago in the United States regarding "green roofs," summarizes their experiences, and provides reference for the future development of "green roof" projects in China.

3. Policy analysis

Green roof projects typically require vegetation to be completely planted on top of the waterproof membrane on the building roof, commonly used in urban skyscraper communities. Additional ecological barriers such as root barriers and drainage irrigation systems have also been established at the top of these buildings. Rooftop ponds are also occasionally used to treat metabolic impurities and greywater in biological systems. Green roofs have multiple uses for buildings, such as absorbing rainwater, lowering urban temperatures, and insulating buildings. This article focuses on the green roof policies of four typical cities in the United States, evaluating factors such as procedures, allocation, and impact on "environmental justice" in existing documents.

3.1 Policy Analysis of Seattle and Denver

In 2007, Seattle passed the draft minimum green requirements for the Seattle Green Factor. This draft stipulates that some new development projects near commercial areas must provide green vegetation coverage exceeding 30% of the applicable area. This regulation applies to development projects with commercial spaces exceeding 370 square meters, or more than 4 residential units, or more than 20 parking spaces. These policies were later officially written into the Seattle Commercial Code and encouraged the planting of larger vegetation, not limited to rooftops. If it is visible to the public, the municipal authorities can provide more incentive policies and support measures. In addition, these regulations also include reward measures for collecting rainwater and planting plants. There is a worksheet attached to the relevant regulations in Seattle to assist applicants in calculating scores and dispatch professionals to assist in reviewing whether various combinations of plant landscapes comply with regulations. The Bullitt Center is the most typical green roof project in Seattle (Figure 1), which utilizes many advanced sustainable development technologies, such as storing and filtering rainwater collected by the green roof through underground reservoirs. In addition, the

toilet is equipped with aerobic devices that can treat and decompose excrement, as well as a solar cell array that can meet the building's annual electricity consumption.

Figure 1 Green roof Project 1

Denver is one of the cities in the United States with the largest urban-rural temperature difference in the past decade, and it is also the area with the most significant urban heat island effect. In 2017, Denver passed a new bill (Proposition 300) on green roof projects, which required most new buildings to install green roofs to reduce heat dissipation. However, this mandatory measure was opposed by Michael Hancock, the then mayor of Denver. He believes that the government should promote green roof projects in an encouraging manner, rather than enforcing them through legislation. The proposal requires buildings with an area exceeding 2300 square meters to install green roofs at the top and requires a 10% increase in green roof area for every 4600 square meters, with a maximum increase of 60% in proportion. In addition, the proposal calls for the establishment of a "Technical Advisory Committee" to ensure the implementation of relevant policies and procedures. At the same time, the Denver City Council has promised that in the next six months, based on the implementation of the bill, it can be modified with the consent of more than two-thirds of the members.

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Figure 2 Green roof project 2

3.2 New York Policy Analysis

According to data released by the New York City Department of Architecture, as of 2022, there are approximately 730 buildings with green roofs in New York City, with a total project area of over 2.4×10^5 square meters. As a vital component of the NYC 7s Climate Mobilization Act, a 'Sus. sustainable roofing zone' is defined as an area with solar panels or green roofs. These bills allow low-income communities to apply for up to 5 years of exemption rights after approval and review by the housing and development department, during which time they are not subject to the Green Roof Enforcement Act. As early as 2008, New York issued a building code that required the roofs of most new buildings to be covered with a 75% reflective white coating or to use energy-efficient high reflective consumer products that comply with the International Energy Star standard. In addition, New York also provides property tax incentives for green roofs. As stipulated in the 2013 New York State S.B.S4802 Property Tax Deduction Amendment, the definition of "green roof" has been expanded, the value of tax deductions has been slightly increased, and the application period has been extended to 5 years.

On June 14, 2017, after experiencing three days of extreme heat waves, New York City Mayor Bill de Blasio announced the launch of a \$106 million plan to "mitigate the threat of the summer urban heat island effect to public health. The policy is named the 'Cool Communities in New York' initiative, with approximately 80% of the investment going towards afforestation in areas such as the northern part of Mahaton and the South Bronx. In the following years, approximately 2.5×10^5 square meters of public and private roofs in New York City were planted with green vegetation or painted white. In addition, there are some related preferential policies in New York, such as a private fee of \$4.5 per square foot for green roof space, which is only a quarter of the total cost (\$20-25). At the same time, the government also hires registered architects and landscape designers to design rooftop spaces and plant drought resistant vegetation for the public free of charge. However, subsequent practice has proven that these plans did not have the expected effect, such as the last preferential policy. Statistics show that within 3 years after the policy was issued, only 4 homeowners applied for the preferential policy. Because most homeowners who can build green roofs are affluent, they do not need these benefits, and most of them live in areas without high rainwater management value, so their demand is not obvious. For poorer communities, they are not yet able to eat enough and will not consider applying these matters.

Based on these policy influences, New York has built many famous "green roof" projects, such as the Green Roof Garden at Rockefeller Center in New York. The chief planner of the complex was Raymond Hood, and it was constructed with the participation of renowned American architect Wallace Harrison. It later became a filming location for many famous films and TV shows. The design of the rooftop garden draws inspiration from the architectural concept of the Babylonian Sky Garden, with pedestrian overpasses connecting to the rooftop garden network, achieving true three-

dimensional greening. The stunning shrubs and flowers, exquisite fountains, and flat lawns make it the oldest and most peaceful green harbor in the bustling New York city while alleviating the urban heat island effect.

3.3 Chicago Policy Analysis

According to data from the Chicago Department of Planning and Development, the city has over 500 plantings and green roofs covering an area of over 5.1 X105 m2, making it the city with the largest green roof area in the United States. The Chicago Department of Architecture has developed an incentive policy called the "Green Elements Permit" to encourage developers and homeowners to install green roofs. In addition, Chicago's sustainable development policies have always been one of the strongest driving forces in the green roof movement. According to this policy, if developers or homeowners want to receive assistance from municipal finance, they must consider installing sustainable development projects such as green roofs. To meet the needs and limitations of diverse groups, the city of Chicago has proposed assorted options to address the issue of installing green roofs for different income groups, such as housing loans, trust funds, low-income housing tax credits, tax-free claims, donation tax credits, and other preferential policies. For example, according to Chicago's zoning regulations, buildings with green roof coverage of 50% or more will receive a building area ratio bonus of \$5000. This reward policy applies to all mixed use building communities in the city center, to alleviate the increasingly severe heat island effect in this area. Related studies have shown that if green roofs were installed on the roof surfaces of all buildings in Chicago, a total of 2046.89 tons of air pollutant would be eliminated. In response to this policy, the Chicago City Government has built one of the world's most famous green roof projects - the "Chicago City Hall Green Roof." In 2001, it was equipped with a total of 3600 square meters of green space, covering over 150 diverse types of 20000 plants. Mayor Richard M. Daley hopes to promote the implementation of green roofs throughout the city through this project, to address the increasingly severe urban heat island problem.

4 Issues and Implications

Although numerous pieces of evidence suggest that green roofs can reduce the heat emitted by buildings and have a significant effect on mitigating urban heat island effects, this is not always the case in practical applications. A study by Columbia University has shown that among numerous green building projects, green roofs are the most unpredictable. It has a unique fungal community that can help plants thrive in harsh and polluted environments, but these communities are not sufficient to establish a complete rooftop ecosystem. At present, the iteration of green roofs heavily relies on a limited number of plant species and lacks the biodiversity required to achieve optimal results. However, some scholars have pointed out that rooftop vegetation must withstand fierce winds, long-term ultraviolet radiation, and unpredictable fluctuations in water resources. Therefore, many projects have chosen Sedum plants. From a sustainable development perspective, this plant is not more environmentally friendly than tar or asphalt.

Mandatory measures are aimed at developers or enterprises, requiring them to consider the later construction of green roofs during the construction phase through the formulation of mandatory legal norms. Incentive measures attempt to encourage ordinary residents, landowners, and other individuals to install green roofs on their own buildings through preferential policies such as bonuses or tax credits. These two types of measures have their own advantages and disadvantages: although mandatory measures are considered accelerators for green roof projects, they may also unfairly force some private property owners to bear excessive social benefit costs; as for the latter, the effect of this preferential policy on low-income or other impoverished communities is not significant. The results indicate that although most policies only focus on the implementation of distributive justice, they do not pay attention to the fair distribution of space and the implementation of procedures and policies. In addition, there are also certain conflicts of interest between private property owners and the public. The benefits brought by green roofs are enjoyed by the public, but the cost is completely shifted onto private homeowners.

In view of this, in the future development of green roof projects in China, two points should be emphasized: firstly, the scientific and rational issues of green roof construction, which mainly involve the selection and maintenance of vegetation in different regions, as well as the correct assessment of the impact on the local ecology; Secondly, in the

process of formulating and implementing incentive policies, in addition to considering the issue of social responsibility and obligation distribution justice, it is also necessary to consider the implementation of “environmental justice”, adopt diverse response measures for different income groups, and increase public participation in policy formulation, taking into account environmental, economic, and social benefits.

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